

Hydrogen Cyanide as a Gasocrine Signal: Perspectives on Potential Hydrogen Cyanide Protogasoreceptors

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In the emerging field of gasocrinology, several important questions remain unanswered (1–4). Hydrogen cyanide (HCN) is an evolutionarily ancient gas (5, 6). HCN is synthesized by various organisms and cells, where it plays diverse roles including defense mechanisms, seed germination, and cellular metabolism (7–9). At physiological pH, HCN largely exists in its undissociated, volatile (gaseous) form, making it a potential gasocrine signaling molecule. This raises the question: What are the identities of HCN-sensing gasoreceptors, riboceptors, or perhaps other classes of biomolecules?

It remains unclear whether such gasoreceptors exist or if they have already been identified but perhaps mislabeled, due to disagreements among experts, or if they have yet to be discovered. This situation is reminiscent of the parable of the blind men and the elephant (10). If these gasoreceptors are still unknown, could they be related to the reported HCN-dependent post-translational modification known as S-cyanylation, or to the need to distinguish between HCN- and cyanide ion-based interactions (11, 12)?

When I proposed hemoglobin as a dioxygen protogasoreceptor within a proto-component signal transduction system, this opened the door to speculation about protogasoreceptors for other gases, including HCN (13, 14). Candidate cyanide (HCN or CN⁻) protoreceptors include *Campylobacter jejuni* truncated hemoglobin P (Cj-trHbP), *Armoracia rusticana* Peroxidase C1A (PRXC1A, also known as Horseradish peroxidase or ferropoxidase), vitamin K-dependent γ -glutamyl carboxylase (GGCX), and cytochrome c oxidase (Complex IV) (15–23). Of these, *C. jejuni* Cj-trHbP is a highly promising HCN protogasoreceptor candidate, followed by *A. rusticana* PRXC1A.

The role of Cj-trHbP has been reported to be that of a dioxygen (O₂) transfer and peroxynitrite scavenging protein (24–26). To definitively prove or disprove the role of this protein as a HCN protogasoreceptor in the proto-component signal transduction system, it is essential to integrate structural data with mutagenesis and biochemical studies on HCN interaction at the enzyme's active site. Additionally, the putative “signaling role” of their enzymatic activity must be investigated, particularly under conditions where competing ligands, such as O₂ or carbon monoxide (CO), cannot bind. Finally, if the binding of these gases results in the inhibition of the enzyme activity, it is tempting to speculate that Cj-trHbP acts as a protogasoreceptor for HCN, O₂, and CO. Other Cj-trHbP orthologs that can bind to HCN must also be considered as potential HCN protogasoreceptors.

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